

Electrochemical Behaviour of Mixed Complexes of Cd(II) with Pyridine and γ -picoline at d.m.e.*

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Cathodic reduction of mixed cadmium-pyridine- γ -picoline complexes has been studied at the d.m.e. It has been found to be reversible and diffusion controlled involving two electron reduction. Three mixed complexes having stoichiometry 1:1:1, 1:1:2 and 1:2:1 are reported. The logarithm of overall formation constants β_{11} , β_{12} and β_{21} for the complexes $[\text{Cd}(\text{pyridine})(\gamma\text{-picoline})]^{2+}$, $[\text{Cd}(\text{pyridine})(\gamma\text{-picoline})_2]^{2+}$ and $[\text{Cd}(\text{pyridine})_2(\gamma\text{-picoline})]^{2+}$ are 2.11, 2.57 and 2.78 respectively. The tendency of complex (simple and mixed) to add and substitute another ligand is discussed.

PYRIDINE and γ -picoline¹ each forms 1:3 highest complexes with Cd(II). Mixed complexation was first of all studied by Schaap and McMasters² using polarographic measurements. The method of Schaap and McMasters has been applied by many others³⁻⁷. With Cd(II) three mixed complexes having stoichiometry 1:1:1, 1:2:1 and 1:1:2 are formed in solution.

Experimental

The solutions of $\text{Cd}(\text{NO}_3)_2$, KNO_3 , pyridine and γ -picoline were prepared in double distilled water. Chemicals used were of reagent grade. The ionic strength was maintained constant at 1.0M using KNO_3 as the supporting electrolyte. The capillary of d.m.e. had the following characteristics $m=2$ mg/sec., $t=4.6$ sec. at the height 66.5 cm of mercury head and the polarograms were obtained manually. The temperature was maintained constant at $30 \pm 1^\circ$ throughout the experiment with the help of Hakke type ultra thermostat. The two fixed concentrations of pyridine used were 0.2M and 0.4M.

Results

Initially the complexes of Cd(II) with the ligands chosen were studied separately. The DeFord and Hume⁸ method of graphical extrapolation was used to determine the overall formation constants of the consecutive simple complexes. The results are summarised below:

Complex	Overall formation constant
$[\text{Cd}(\text{Py})]^{2+}$	β_{01} 20
$[\text{Cd}(\text{Py})_2]^{2+}$	β_{02} 50
$[\text{Cd}(\text{Py})_3]^{2+}$	β_{03} 65
$[\text{Cd}(\gamma\text{-pic})]^{2+}$	β_{10} 60
$[\text{Cd}(\gamma\text{-pic})_2]^{2+}$	β_{20} 300
$[\text{Cd}(\gamma\text{-pic})_3]^{2+}$	β_{30} 440

TABLE 1—POLAROGRAPHIC MEASUREMENT AND Fij FUNCTIONS OF Cd(II)- γ -PICOLINE-PYRIDINE MIXED COMPLEXES AT 303°K.

$-E_{1/2}$ of simple metal ion = 0.6090 volts vs. SCE
 i_d of simple metal ion = 69 div.
ionic strength = 1.0 M
[Pyridine] = 0.20 M fixed

C_X (γ -picoline) mole litre ⁻¹	$-E_{1/2}$ Vs. S.C.E.	i_d (div.)	F_{00}	F_{10}	F_{20}	F_{30}
0.0	0.6090	69.0	—	—	—	—
0.1	0.6440	51.0	19.86	128.6	286	—
0.2	0.6554	48.0	47.23	201.1	505	425
0.3	0.6620	47.0	85.76	262.5	541	405
0.4	0.6685	47.0	141.30	335.7	589	423
0.5	0.6740	47.0	215.40	416.8	633	427
0.6	0.6785	46.0	310.90	506.5	677	429
0.7	0.6830	46.0	439.10	617.2	738	455

A = 7, B = 100, C = 420 and $D_{av} = 425$.

TABLE 2—POLAROGRAPHIC MEASUREMENT AND Fij FUNCTIONS OF Cd(II)- γ -PICOLINE-PYRIDINE MIXED COMPLEXES AT 303°K.

$-E_{1/2}$ of simple metal ion = 0.6090 volts vs. S.C.E.
 i_d of simple metal ion = 69 div.
ionic strength = 1.0 M
[Pyridine] = 0.40 M fixed.

C_X (γ -picoline) mole litre ⁻¹	$-E_{1/2}$ Vs. S.C.E.	i_d (div)	F_{00}	F_{10}	F_{20}	F_{30}
0.0	0.6090	69	—	—	—	—
0.1	0.6535	49	42.85	228.5	585	450
0.2	0.6610	47	79.43	297.1	635	475
0.3	0.6675	47	130.80	369.3	664	414
0.4	0.6730	46	204.10	460.1	725	462
0.5	0.6775	44	301.00	562.0	784	488
0.6	0.6810	42	412.70	654.5	807	445
0.7	0.6850	42	561.00	772.8	861	458

A = 20, B = 170, C = 540 and $D_{av} = 450$

$\beta_{11} = 130$, $\beta_{12} = 375$ and $\beta_{21} = 600$.

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The polarographic characteristics of mixed Cd(II)-pyridine and γ -picoline at fixed concentration of pyridine 0.2M and 0.4M are presented in Tables 1 and 2. From the two sets of A, B, C and D values $\beta_{1,1}$, $\beta_{1,2}$ and $\beta_{2,1}$ have been evaluated and are shown in Table 2.

Discussion

The equilibria among the various complexes present in solution is schematically shown below :

Scheme

In the above scheme the numerical values are the log K values where K is the equilibrium constants of the step indicated in the summary. From the above scheme following conclusions are drawn.

The equilibrium constant for the addition reaction of Y to $[Cd(Y)]^{2+}$ is less than the addition reaction of X to $[Cd(Y)]^{2+}$ which shows mixed complexation is favourable over the simple complex formation if a metal ion is present in the mixture of two ligands. The

same may be concluded from the equilibrium constants of addition reactions of X to $[Cd(X)]^{2+}$ and Y to $[Cd(X)]^{2+}$, where X and Y stands for γ -picoline and pyridine concentration respectively.

X adds to $[Cd(Y)_2]^{2+}$ more easily than to $[Cd(X)_2]^{2+}$ and Y adds more easily to $[Cd(X)_2]^{2+}$ than to $[Cd(X)_3]^{2+}$ (see summary). These facts also favour mixed complexation.

It is seen that $[Cd(X)_2]^{2+}$ can substitute Y and $[Cd(Y)_2]^{2+}$ can substitute X and $[Cd(X)(Y)]^{2+}$ can substitute X and not Y. The former statement supports mixed complexation and the latter one shows that X is a stronger ligand than Y.

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